

SOME FEATURES OF SYNTACTIC PARADIGM

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Annotation: *This article analyzes the features, significance and place of the concept of syntactic paradigm in speech. Definitions given in modern linguistics, opinions of scientists are studied and analyzed. Many linguists have analyzed the various definitions, the simplest concept of the syntactic paradigm, according to which it includes both a sentence and a phrase.*

Key words: *syntactic paradigm; syntagmatic relations; language system, morphotactics, Systemic Functional Linguistic, transformational method; semantic equivalence; invariant value; morphological paradigm; core; predicate; modification.*

Introduction

In recent years, a special focus on science and education has placed researchers in positions of responsibility in both theoretical and practical fields. One such task is to learn and teach foreign languages. Significant work is being done in our country to develop the study of foreign languages.

As an example, to create conditions for the development of students' basic language skills (listening, reading, writing and speaking), including the organization of in-depth study of foreign languages by merging foreign language departments of higher education institutions; introduction of internationally recognized methods of teaching students in foreign languages and assessment of their knowledge, including the widespread use of distance and other modern forms of education in the educational process, as well as the teaching of other subjects in foreign languages; ensuring that students' mastery of at least two foreign languages broadens their horizons, increases their potential, and increases their competitiveness in the labor market [1].

The development of linguistic science over the past decades is characterized by intensive development problems of syntactic paradigm. The concept of "syntactic paradigm" is one of the latest linguistic concepts. It is a logical continuation of the idea of the need to combine the consideration of paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations, the interdependence of which is now recognized by all [2].

Methodology

Linguists and semioticians specialising in lexicology, syntax, semantics, stylistics, rhetoric, discourse analysis, pragmatics and semiotics are invited to contribute to this thematic issue that will seek to renew the “paradigm” concept; firstly, it lies at the centre of some theoretical formulations (*Systemic Functional Linguistics*), and secondly, it has been marginalised and used only didactically. Therefore, it loses its major explanatory nature, both in terms of the organisation of language, and the description of discourse.

The paradigm was a concept at the foundation of a scientific perspective on languages. However, there were still some ambiguities. On the one hand, the paradigmatic organisation affirmed the existence of *classes* of elements characterizing specifically the *language* system, and the other hand the criteria for the classifications appeared as heterogeneous and external to the autonomous form of *language* (associations, resemblances, etc.). If there was a problem with limiting this hybridisation of the internal principles to linguistic functioning, the paradigm provided in return a principle of mobilization of forms, showing the tensions *between* the classes and *inside* the classes. The system did not provide a neutral background made of pure *virtualities*: competing classifications could be recognized in the system and, in the same paradigm, contradictory tensions were also found between morphotactics compliance of the same root, and the introduction of irregular forms.

Syntactic paradigmatics owes its formation to the transformational method. In transformational grammar, a paradigm is understood as a series of structurally different, but semantically correlative constructions, i.e. transformational paradigmatics is based on the concept of semantic equivalence. The concept of "syntactic paradigm" can be interpreted broadly as the result of an action any grammatical categories covering the statement, and narrowly, referring to them only those sets syntactic classifications, which differ in the nature of syntactic relations.

The syntactic paradigm established by T. P. Lomtev is based on the sign of convertibility relations between predicative objects [3]. M. Ya. Bloch understands the syntactic paradigm as “a number of language structures correlated and united at the syntactic level according to the generalized (exemplary) variant-invariant feature of the expression of categorical meaning” [4]. The broadest understanding of the syntactic paradigm, according to which the latter is defined as a complex of correlating syntactic structures that differ by at least one morpheme, includes both a sentence and a phrase in the syntactic paradigm [5]. Indeed, since we are talking

about a syntactic paradigm, its members should be units of the syntactic level: a sentence and a phrase. According to some linguists [6], the phrase paradigms are not syntactic, but represent the sum of morphological paradigms. For example, the paradigms of the phrase this book, these books are based on the system of forms of the stem word of the phrase. linguists, dealing with problems of syntax agree that the units of the syntactic paradigm are suggestions.

Discussion and results

Today the paradigm concept can work in an antiphrastic way: firstly, as a reformulation of what can be really attributed to the system of language in the continuous transformation of its forms; and secondly, as a review of the discursive significance that functions as a “sounding board” for competitive meaning effects.

Certain questions seem to require the attention of the linguist and the semiotician:

- What are the historical conditions for identifying a paradigmatic classification?
 - How can a language be distinguished from other competing semiotic organisations, based on its internal paradigms?
 - How can a speech “weave” its own paradigmatic organisations?
 - What are the tactical discursive forms of exploitation of the linguistic paradigmatic potentialities?
 - Does paradigmatic organisation compete with syntax coordination as regard to discursive semantic effects?
 - Can paradigms guarantee a prior mapping of speech, capable of qualifying enunciative choices?
 - Can the paradigm participate in the structural and categorical architecture of language, or is it the first apprehension of a semiotic development environment, where the living activity of assimilation and dissimilation can be found, which ultimately unifies linguistic system and discourse?

The paradigm concept has experienced competition from other linguistic and semiotic concepts; there is not only a significant interest in the “archaeological” analysis of distinctions, but also the necessity to proceed with other dissimilations. For example, according to the theory of M.A.K. Halliday, we can acknowledge the leading role of paradigmatic organisation easily, but afterwards we could prefer to use the concepts of “system networks” and “meaning potential of language”.

In a narrower and thus clearer form, the sentence paradigm is outlined in the concept of N. Yu. Shvedova, which includes forms in the sentence paradigm that differ in signs of syntactic tense and objective modality. Such paradigms are based on the same grammatical categories that organize the morphological forms of the sentence. Despite, however, the closeness to the morphological paradigm, the sentence paradigm is characterized in this concept as syntactic: its members are syntactic (rather than morphological) sentence forms in which differences in signs of time are expressed not only by changes in the verb, but also by differences in the structure suggestions. The syntactic paradigm is built for all possible sentence patterns, while the morphological paradigm is applicable only to "classical" verb sentences [7,].

Conclusion

To sum up, it may be emphasised that the term paradigm was used to describe the internal organisation of grammatical classifications, and, therefore, to also name the inflectional forms of verbs, beyond the use of multiple stems. This illustrates that its modelling scope was acknowledged not only as a taxemic homogeneity, compared to the heterogeneity of assembled lexemes, but also as a heterogeneity of forms in the declination of the same word.

Above, we have only considered the specifics of syntactic paradigm. If we analyze other branch of paradigm in the same way, it becomes clear that they have their own stylistic, semantic features, the scope of their use, their versatility and differ from other concepts.

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